

ADVANCING METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO HOUSING CONSTRUCTION IN THE CONTEXT OF URBANIZATION

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Abstract. *In this article, modern housing construction is presented as a complex multi-level system that is continuously developing both in space and time. The principles, tasks, functions and methods of three interrelated areas are considered - housing construction, urbanization and regional economy. Based on the identification of contradictions between the components of these areas, it is proposed to supplement them with new principles, tasks and methods, in particular the principle of an integral and comprehensive approach. Thus, the improvement of the methodology of housing construction in the context of active urbanization is substantiated. Also, the experience of developed countries in scientific and digital planning of residential development is analyzed, giving the microdistrict the status of a key unit of sustainable and managed urban growth.*

Keywords: *housing construction, residential microdistrict, housing stock, development structure, infrastructure, urbanization, regional economy, algorithm, insolation, drainage, instrumental system, optimization, pattern recognition.*

Introduction

The main strategic goal of economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a sustainable and progressive increase in the material well-being and cultural standard of living of the population. Achieving this goal requires accelerating socio-economic progress, intensifying production processes and increasing the efficiency of the national economy based on the introduction of scientific and technological progress and modern management approaches.

The foundation of the long-term socio-economic development of the country is the formation of a safe, functional and comfortable living environment capable of satisfying the current and future needs of the population. In the context of global urbanization, there is a steady increase in the number of urban residents throughout the world. According to forecasts of the United Nations, by 2050 the proportion of the population living in cities will reach 70% [1]. This trend determines the need to modernize urban infrastructure, create a favorable social environment and ensure conditions for harmonious interaction between citizens.

Within the framework of the state policy, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government are implementing the following key areas [1], [2]:

- Improving the urbanization policy aimed at improving housing conditions, developing social infrastructure, expanding the service sector and creating an environmentally sustainable urban environment, including bringing the level of greening in Tashkent to 30%.
- Implementing a new housing policy that provides for measures of state support for housing construction with the provision of the necessary engineering and social infrastructure.

- Developing measures to develop social infrastructure, protect built-up areas from emergency situations through engineering and planning solutions, as well as forming a general settlement plan taking into account long-term forecasts.

- Implementing the Program for the Development of Social and Industrial Infrastructure of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2024–2026.

- Approving in the general plan of Tashkent the parameters of sustainable development density, directions of socio-economic development and measures to meet the current and future needs of the population.

In modern conditions, along with the increase in the volume of housing construction, the improvement of scientific, methodological and applied approaches to planning urban infrastructure is of particular importance. Achieving economic efficiency in housing construction is possible only with the integration of modern methods of analysis and forecasting of socio-economic development with the optimal design of the urban environment. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the density of development, energy efficiency, engineering safety, environmental requirements and demographic dynamics. This determines the need to use scientifically sound methods and digital technologies that ensure high quality design solutions.

The effective solution to this problem is possible only on the basis of a comprehensive assessment of demographic, social, economic, environmental and technological factors. This involves revising the ratio of elements of the living environment (green areas, children's and sports grounds, educational institutions, service facilities) and the parameters of residential development.

Existing challenges and goals set by the state determine the need to use methods of multi-criteria optimization of the housing stock and the structure of development of microdistricts, taking into account social, economic and environmental priorities.

The spatial organization of settlements and socio-cultural factors that shape the urban environment are the subject of complex interdisciplinary study. This area covers research in the framework of sociology, urban planning, architecture, economics and related applied sciences. Its complexity is determined by the need to integrate data on the quality of the urban environment, the level of socio-economic development, lifestyle of the population, cultural potential and the structure of communications, taking into account organizational, financial and infrastructural constraints.

Modern cities, including Tashkent, face persistent problems in the areas of housing and communal services, transport, energy supply, improvement and provision of affordable housing. The solution to these problems requires a comprehensive approach, including architectural design, landscaping and the development of comfortable microdistricts as basic units of urban development.

In the context of multiple factors and constraints, effective urban planning decisions cannot be made without the use of multi-criteria and multi-variant methods. The limitations of traditional approaches that consider a narrow set of design solutions lead to the fact that the final results may differ from the actual indicators by 15-20%, and an overrun of 1-2% on the scale of Tashkent is equivalent to annual additional costs of several billion soums [6].

Analysis of urbanization and housing construction problems in Uzbekistan. Modern development of the region is impossible without understanding the systemic relationship of three key categories - urbanization, regional economy and microdistrict planning.

Urbanization transforms the territorial structure, increases demand for housing and infrastructure, while developing socio-economic aspects. True urbanization implies a balance

between the population and the level of infrastructure provision. Its violation leads to false urbanization, typical for a number of cities in Asia and Latin America, where migration from depressed regions leads to overpopulation with a low level of amenities. The example of China demonstrates how demographic policy and urbanization are interconnected: during the reform period, the share of the urban population increased from 20% to 65%, social norms and attitudes towards the birth rate changed.

The rapid redistribution of the population from rural areas to cities requires the formation of methodological foundations for the development of housing construction and the identification of scientific principles and methods that ensure its effectiveness. Actual issues include:

- the growth of the urban population is outpacing the growth of the rural population, while the city of Tashkent is experiencing a burden on the housing stock and the corresponding infrastructure. This creates an urgent need to expand housing construction, modernize infrastructure and develop scientifically sound design and implementation mechanisms;

- the necessity to develop and implement a Strategy for the Development of Large Cities, envisaging the city as a separate independent center;

- significant differences in population density. For example, in the city of Tashkent it (6900 people / km²) is more than 80 times higher than the national average (83.6 people / km²);

- infrastructure problems: insufficient provision of public utilities is one of the serious problems of urbanization;

- delayed implementation of an effective system and mechanisms based on modern forecasting models, as well as insufficient consideration of demographic factors when placing objects. An effective solution to these problems requires the introduction of scientifically based approaches and technologies;

- lack of information data and tools for effective forecasting and design caused by the rapid development of the city. The lack of information on the land plots on which satellite cities are being built limits the adoption of effective measures for efficient land use.

The Government of the Republic is consistently implementing a policy in the field of housing construction:

- the goal has been formulated - to accelerate urbanization and increase the share of the urban population to 60% by 2030. This requires a systematic elaboration of the concept of urban development and the implementation of practical measures in urban planning;

- the Strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" sets the task of providing the population with affordable housing and high-quality infrastructure;

- The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan [2] provides for the activation of urbanization processes based on the implementation of a new housing policy, which provides for the construction of residential buildings with the provision of engineering and social infrastructure;

- the approved general plan of the city of Tashkent provides the opportunity to choose various construction conditions taking into account the current economic conditions [3].

If the construction volume remains at least 600 thousand square meters over the next 5-7 years (until 2030), the total volume will be 3,000-4,200 thousand square meters by the end of the period. The total volume of housing in the city will reach 36.0-37.0 million square meters of total area, which will provide at least 18.2 square meters per person. According to the general plan of the city of Tashkent, by 2030, the annual commissioning of housing will increase to 44,000 apartments (an increase of 45%) with the corresponding comfort of infrastructure facilities. The

bulk of the volumes will be located in new territories, which will preserve the existing housing stock.

World experience and its adaptation. Developed countries have accumulated significant experience in scientific and digital planning of residential development, giving the microdistrict (Stadtquartier, Quartier, Neighborhood) the status of a key unit of sustainable and managed urban growth. Among the most advanced models are the German engineering-systems, the French social-humanitarian and the American digital-oriented, each of which has its own architecture of scientific and regulatory implementation.

- Germany relies on a developed research and technical infrastructure (Fraunhofer, TU München, DLR, etc.), actively uses multi-criteria optimization models, GIS, BIM, digital twins and scenario-based forecasting. Here, sustainability (energy, climate), transport connectivity, insolation and participation of residents play a key role. The concepts of Smart City, Null-Emissionsquartier and Passivhaus formed the basis of dozens of microdistricts - from Vauban (Freiburg) to HafenCity (Hamburg);

- France, in turn, focuses on social inclusion, short-term accessibility and reconstruction of the urban landscape. The approaches are based on the concept of ville du quart d'heure ("15-minute city"), which forms local sustainability and autonomy of the microdistrict. French research institutes (CSTB, ParisTech, ANRU) develop agent-based models, life cycle assessments of buildings (LCA), and digital methods for forecasting social mobility. The practice of citizen participation in territorial management is widely used;

- The United States approaches microdistrict planning based on deep scenario modeling, smart city technologies, risk assessment tools, and economic and spatial models. Key research centers are the MIT Department of Urban Studies and Planning, Harvard Graduate School of Design, Berkeley College of Environmental Design, as well as the Brookings Institution, Urban Land Institute (ULI). American practice is built around Neighborhood planning and Community-based Design, where both modeling of infrastructure sustainability and digital simulation of processes in real time are important. Digital twin platforms (UrbanSim, CityEngine, Sidewalk Labs), IoT technologies, BIM 360, ArcGIS Urban, forecasting of housing demand, transport load and energy consumption are widespread;

- in Japan, scientific design of microdistricts (ちいきまちづくり - "creation of a comfortable urban environment in a specific area") is implemented through university consortiums, private development and urban planning bureaus, as well as planning institutes. The leading institutions are: the University of Tokyo (UTokyo), Nagoya University, the National Institute of Land, Infrastructure and Transport Research (MLIT NLI). Japan actively applies the CASBEE (Comprehensive Assessment System for Built Environment Efficiency) system - a national standard for assessing the sustainability of microdistricts. Digital twin platforms integrated with early warning systems for emergencies are being developed.

These countries demonstrate a high level of digitalization and sustainable development. For example, in Germany, digital technology is a mandatory element of federal construction programs, and the Passivhaus and Plusenergiehaus energy standards are set as the norm. In Japan, there is a unique Machizukuri Institute, where residents develop local development plans together with municipalities.

The analysis of the scientific experience of developed countries allows us to identify the following strategic models for designing microdistricts:

- Germany is a leader in scientific and engineering modeling of a sustainable microdistrict with digital modeling and energy sustainability;

- France is a center of social inclusion and landscape-urban planning; the socio-ecological model of the "15-minute city" with an emphasis on local infrastructure;

- The USA is a digital and institutional leader with strong forecasting tools;

- Japan is an example of cultural, demographic and earthquake-resistant adaptation of a microdistrict.

Despite the high level of scientific and technological development in the field of residential environment design, the experience of developed countries is not without shortcomings and contradictions, especially when adapting it to the conditions of other countries, including Uzbekistan.

These recommendations allow for a more critical approach to the transfer of scientific models to Uzbekistan, to determine which elements are actually applicable and where localization is needed, taking into account the specifics of the region: climate, regulatory framework, population density and socio-cultural structure.

The above analysis determines the need to develop new methodological approaches to optimizing the housing stock and the planning structure of microdistricts in the context of urbanization - the development of housing construction will be ensured by [5]:

- Improving the mechanisms and methods of territorial regulation that take into account the relationship of economic, demographic and urban planning factors;

- Expanding the methodological apparatus of mathematical modeling of problems of optimizing the housing stock and infrastructure;

- Formation of principles for building integrated management systems adapted to the tasks of strategic and tactical planning at the microdistrict level.

The author has developed a set of models, algorithms and software solutions, including:

- Economic and mathematical models of demographic forecasting of the quantitative and qualitative composition of the population.

- Algorithms for calculating insolation characteristics and parameters of drainage systems of various types.

- Methods for optimizing the structure of housing stock and the configuration of microdistrict development.

- A problem-oriented tool system for designers and managers.

- A module for applying pattern recognition methods to integrate forecasting, optimization and decision-making processes within the framework of a triune planning task [4].

Conclusion

The approach developed and implemented in practice allows for the formation of scientifically sound solutions that ensure a balance between the functional, environmental and social efficiency of the planned residential environment.

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